

PREPARATION AND MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF CARBON NANOFIBER REINFORCED THREE-PHASE CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

The superior mechanical properties of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and carbon nanofibers (CNFs) make them the ideal candidates for composite reinforcement. Although some experimental measurements indicated the enhancement of strength with the addition of CNTs into the polymer matrix, results without or with limited strength enhancement were also reported [1,2]. Two important issues concerning the applications of CNTs and CNFs in the composite reinforcement need to be overcome. The first is the uniform dispersion of these nano-reinforcing materials in the polymer matrix. The second is the effective stress transfer from the CNTs to the composite. For the effective stress transfer, the bonding between the reinforcement and the matrix should be strong, which makes the surface properties of the CNTs and CNFs important. Recently, incorporation of CNTs or CNFs in carbon fiber (CF)/polymer composites to form a hybrid multiscale composite was proposed and enhancements of mechanical behavior were reported for CF/polymer [3-6] and glass fiber/polymer [7-9] composites. The properties of carbon nanomaterials based composites primarily depend on the dispersion of nanomaterials in the matrix of composites. Agglomeration of nanofillers leads to the generation of potential defects and thereby deteriorates composite properties. Hence the selection of an efficient dispersion technique for nanofillers prior to the fabrication of three-phase composites is extremely important. To date, four major approaches have been developed [10,11]: (1) infusion of a CNT-/CNF-resin mixture into the preform, (2) direct growth of CNTs/CNFs on reinforcement fabric substrates, (3) direct placement of CNTs/CNFs between layers of the preform, and (4)

electrophoretic deposition of CNTs/CNFs on reinforcement fabric substrates. Discussion of these methods can be found in the literature [10,11].

Compared with the polymer matrix composites, few investigations [12] were reported on the reinforcement of carbon fiber reinforced carbon matrix (C-C) composites with the incorporation of CNTs or CNFs. Therefore, in this investigation, CNFs were grown on CF by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) using Ni catalysts prepared by electrodeposition and then the CNF/CF/carbon matrix three-phase C-C composites were fabricated and their mechanical behavior was investigated.

2 Experimental

2.1 Sample preparation

Plain woven PAN-based CF was used as the substrate for the growth of CNFs. A three-electrode assembly cell was adopted for the electrodeposition, wherein a Pt plate acted as a counter electrode and an Ag/AgCl as reference electrode, and CF with a dimension of $5 \times 5 \text{ cm}^2$ as the working electrode. Nickel ionic electrolyte (0.5 M) was prepared using nickel chloride dissolved in deionized water. The pH value of electrolyte was maintained at 2 using hydrochloric acid and the deposition was carried out at room temperature. A Basytec Battery Test System (10V/2A By BaSyTec GmbH) was used for the electrodeposition. Growth of CNFs on CF, CNFs/CF, was carried out in a three-zone tube furnace. After the reduction of catalysts in a hydrogen atmosphere at 400°C for 1 hr, the CNFs were grown at 480°C and 500°C using acetylene as the carbon source. For the methane carbon source, a reaction temperature of 1173 K was used. Four different CNF/CF samples were fabricated using different electroplating parameters and CNF growth parameters as indicated

in Table 1. Fig. 1 shows a typical SEM image of CNFs grown on CF fabric. As shown, the CNFs can be grown uniformly and densely on the CF with a narrow range of diameter. The CNFs had a crooked morphology and formed a three-dimensional network structure. After the growth, the CNF/CF samples were used to fabricate CNF/CF/phenolic resin three-phase nanocomposites using vacuum bag hot pressing technique. The phenolic resin used in this study is the resole-type phenol-formaldehyde resin (PF650) manufactured by Chang Chun Plastics Company, Taiwan. For the fabrication of C-C composites, the phenolic resin based three-phase nanocomposites were cut, weighed and then carbonized at 1000 and 1400°C. The carbonization treatment is performed using a three-zone tube furnace under an argon atmosphere. The heating rate from ambient temperature to 1000°C was 2°C/min and was 5°C/min from 1000 to 1400°C. The hold time is 30 min. at 1000 and 1400°C.

Table 1 CNF/CF samples used in this study.

CNF/CF sample	Sample I	Sample II	Sample III	Sample IV
Electroplating parameters	DC -0.75V 5 min		DC -0.75V 3 min	
CNF Growth parameters	500°C 15 min	480°C 15 min	480°C 15 min	480°C 8 min

Fig.1. SEM image of carbon nanofibers grown on carbon fiber fabrics (CNF/CF sample I).

2.2 Characterization

The mechanical properties and fracture behavior were studied using the three-point bending test according to ASTM D-790. The rectangular plate samples were cut from the composite panel. The dimensions of the samples were about 30 × 10 × 0.8 mm³. The support span was 20 mm and the crosshead speed was 0.5 mm/min. A universal material testing machine (LLOYD-LF plus, UK) was used for the three-point test. Five samples were tested for each category and the average value was reported. The morphology of the CNF grown on carbon fiber fabric and the fracture surfaces of the composites after flexural test were observed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Phenolic resin composites

Figure 2 shows the flexural strength of CNF/CF/phenolic resin three-phase nanocomposites, prepared using different CNF/CF samples (samples I ~ IV) as described in Table 1. No strength enhancement was found when CNFs were incorporated in the composites. The CNF growth yields of these CNF/CF samples are also presented in Fig.2. As shown, when the catalyst electroplating time, CNF growth temperature, or CNF growth time was decreased, the growth amount of CNFs was reduced. It is interesting to find that as the CNF growth yield increased, the flexural strength decreased. The reason could be attributed to that when too much amount of CNFs were grown on the CF cloth, more formation of defects could result from the composite fabrication process. Consequently, the average flexural strength of the composite decreased. According to the growth yield measurements, sample IV had the lowest CNF growth amount, and therefore, the higher average strength was obtained when compared with those of sample I, II and III.

Instead of growing CNFs directly on CFs, most research incorporated CNTs/CNFs in the CF composites by dispersing the CNTs/CNFs in the polymer matrix [3-9]. Most results indicated that the best loading amount of CNTs/CNFs was around 0.3~2 wt%. It must be noticed that the calculation of loading amount is usually based on the weight of

resin matrix, but in this study, the CNF growth yield is based on the weight of CF fabric. After calculation, the 5.75 wt% CNF growth yield for the sample IV corresponds to about 10 wt% of CNF loading, which is much larger than the reported best loading amount mentioned previously. Therefore, the flexural strength of sample IV was still lower than that of composite without CNF addition.

Fig. 2 Flexural strength of the three-phase phenolic resin-based nanocomposites prepared using different CNF/CF samples and CNF growth yield of these CNF/CF samples: (A) without CNFs, (B) sample IV, (C) sample III, (D) sample II, and (E) sample I.

To get inside the fracture behavior, the fractographs of the three-phase nanocomposites were examined after flexural tests and the SEM images of the fracture surface of the three-phase nanocomposites, are presented in Fig.3. As shown in Fig.3(a), the phenolic resin matrix without CNFs has a relatively flat and smooth fracture surface (area B and C). Cleavage steps can be seen, but the cleavage plane between the steps shows featureless surface. On the other hand, a rough surface (area A) of the phenolic resin matrix was observed on the CF surface where the CNFs were grown. Fig. 3(b) is the high magnification SEM image of the square region in Fig. 3(a). CNFs can be found in the matrix as pointed out by the arrow signs. The rougher surface associated with the addition of CNF indicated that the fracture behavior could be changed from a brittle type with cleavage featureless surfaces to a more gracious one with a rougher surface as reported by other researchers [4,5]. However, due to the too much amount of CNFs grown on the CF surface, the high density CNFs resulted in the high defect

content during the composite fabrication, and consequently, a loose fracture surface was found as shown in Fig.3(a) and (b) and a lower flexural strength was obtained. Due to the high defect content, cracks were also easily formed in a wriggly manner as shown in Fig. 3(a).

Fig. 3 (a) SEM image of the fracture surface of the three-phase phenolic resin based nanocomposites and (b) the high magnification SEM image of the square region in (a).

3.2 Carbon-carbon Composites

The above mentioned CNF/CF/phenolic resin three-phase nanocomposites were carbonized at 1000°C and 1400°C to convert into C-C composites and their flexural test results are presented in Fig. 4. The corresponding fractographs after flexural tests are shown in Fig. 5. As indicated in Fig. 4(A), the C-C composites carbonized at 1000°C showed a low

flexural strength of 34 MPa as compared with 445 MPa of the corresponding phenolic resin composites (Fig.2). The reason has been well established [13,14] and is because of the formation of brittle glassy carbon matrix after 1000°C carbonization. Due to the strong bonding between the CF/matrix interface as shown in Fig. 5(a), a matrix-dominated brittle fracture was resulted with a much lower strength and a flat fracture surface was observed, indicating a brittle type of failure. A lot of pores were also observed in Fig. 5(a) due to the decomposition of phenolic resin matrix during the carbonization. The introduction of CNFs in the composites further reduced the strength (Fig. 4(B) and 4(C)) due to the increased amount of defects from the composite fabrication process. These defects are detrimental especially for the brittle matrix C-C composites. Increase of carbonization temperature from 1000°C to 1400°C improved the flexural strength of the composites (Fig. 4(D)) although the composites still failed in a brittle way (Fig. 5(b)). As pointed out by Tzeng and Chr [13], two possible reasons could be attributed to the increase of strength. First is the increase of the fiber strength and second is the enhancement of the fiber strength utilization [15,16] due to the weakening of fiber/matrix interface [15,17] when carbonized at 1400°C. The weakening of fiber/matrix interface could be supported from the fracture surface as shown in Fig. 5(c). Although the fracture surface is relatively flat, small steps between the CFs could be observed as compared with the fracture surface of composites carbonized at 1000°C (Fig. 5(a)). Decrease of pore size was also observed at the fracture surface of 1400°C carbonized composites due to the further shrinkage of the composites from 1000°C to 1400°C, which is also beneficial to the strength enhancement. Further strength enhancement was found when the CNFs were incorporated into the composites (Fig. 4(E) and (F)). The reason for this is attributed to the further weakening of fiber/matrix interface as the CNFs were grown on the surface of CFs. As shown in Fig. 5(d) for the fracture surface of composites prepared using the CNF/CF sample (sample III), we saw a lot of fiber/matrix debonding and a relatively uneven fracture surface due to crack branching was seen, indicating that the composites failed in a more gracious way. The further weakening of fiber/matrix interface for the CNF-incorporated composites

raised the fiber strength utilization, leading to the increase of flexural strength. It is also interesting to note that the C-C composites prepared using sample III (Fig. 4(F)) possessed higher strength than that using sample IV (Fig. 4(E)) presumably due to the introduction of more weak interfaces.

Fig.4. Flexural strength of the three-phase carbon-carbon composites prepared using different CNF/CF samples and carbonization temperatures: (A) without CNFs, 1000°C, (B) sample IV, 1000°C, (C) sample III, 1000°C, (D) without CNFs, 1400°C, (E) sample IV, 1400°C and (F) sample III, 1400°C.

Fig.5. SEM images of the fracture surfaces of the three-phase C-C nanocomposites: (a) without CNFs at 1000°C, (b) with CNF/CF (sample III) at 1000°C, (c) without CNFs at 1400°C and (d) with CNF/CF (sample III) at 1400°C.

Figure 6 presents the fracture surface parallel to the fiber direction of the three-phase C-C nanocomposites carbonized at 1400°C. Area A and B in Fig.6 are the pure carbon matrix fracture surfaces, showing brittle and flat cleavage surfaces with many cleavage steps. Circled areas show the fracture surfaces containing CNFs. An enlarged SEM image of circled area C is presented in the insert. CNFs can be observed as indicated by the arrow signs. Contrary to the flat surface of pure carbon matrix, rough surfaces were found for the CNF-containing areas as can be seen at the circled areas in Fig.6. These areas raised the fracture energy when the crack propagated parallel to the fiber direction through the brittle carbon matrix. They also weakened the bonding between carbon fiber and matrix and, consequently, increased the fiber strength utilization when the crack propagated perpendicular to the fiber direction as discussed in Fig. 5(d).

Fig.6. SEM image of the fracture surface parallel to the fiber direction of the three-phase C-C nanocomposites carbonized at 1400°C.

Figure 7 shows the macroscopic fracture surfaces of the three-phase C-C nanocomposites. As shown in Fig.7(a) and 7(b), C-C composites carbonized at 1000°C all showed a typical brittle fracture no matter whether the CNFs were added or not. Transverse cracks [13,14,18] as pointed by the arrow signs could be seen. These cracks, running relatively perpendicularly between two fiber bundles, resulted

from the tensile stresses caused by the carbonization shrinkage of resin matrix [14]. The fracture surfaces of the composites blocks between the transverse cracks are flat as shown previously in Fig. 5(a) and 5(b). As the carbonization temperature was raised to 1400°C, the fracture surface became relatively uneven (Fig. 7(c)). More irregular fracture surfaces can be seen (Fig. 7(d)) as the CNFs were incorporated into the composites due to the further weakening of fiber/matrix interface as discussed previously.

Above results showed that no strength enhancement was found with a CNF addition for the phenolic resin based composites and their corresponding C-C composites at 1000°C. However, comparison between the strength of composites carbonized at 1400°C indicated that a 29.5% increase in flexural strength can be obtained when CNFs were grown on the CF fibers and incorporated into the composites.

Fig. 7. SEM images of the macroscopic fracture surfaces of the three-phase C-C nanocomposites: (a) without CNFs at 1000°C, (b) with CNF/CF(sample III) at 1000°C, (c) without CNFs at 1400°C and (d) with CNF/CF(sample III) at 1400°C.

4. Conclusions

Nickel catalyst nanoparticles can be deposited on the surface of carbon fiber cloth by using electro-deposition technique. The CNFs with uniform distributions of diameter and morphology can be grown uniformly on the carbon fiber cloth by chemical vapor deposition using acetylene as the carbon source. Enhancement of the flexural strength of phenolic resin-based nanocomposites was not achieved due to the relatively large amount of CNF growth. The flexural strength of carbon/carbon nanocomposites carbonized at 1000 °C was also lower than that of the corresponding composites without CNF addition. However, a 29.5% increase in flexural strength was measured when the carbon/carbon nanocomposites were further heat treated at 1400 °C.

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